

MEDICAL SCIENCES

ASSESSMENT OF PHYSICAL DEVELOPMENT, MOTOR TRAINING AND GROWTH DISORDERS FOR SECONDARY SCHOOL STUDENTS FROM RURAL SCHOOLS OF THE REPUBLIC OF MOLDOVA

Zavalişca A.

doctor, university professor associate, State University of Physical Education and Sport, Chisinau, Moldova

Abstract

In this publication are described the results of the research of a group of students from rural localities, from different geographical areas of the country. The aim of the research is to evaluate the degree of physical and motor development of the growing generation, as well as to highlight the presence of some ailments and health disorders.

Keywords: development, growth, affection.

Actuality: Humanity is now passing through the healthiest stage in history in terms of the low number of deaths related to malnutrition and infectious diseases.

Namely, the industrial food revolution and the appearance of modern research, led to a greater increase in the food source, respectively to a rapid population increase. With the growth of the population, the number of ailments increased again, but it decreased after the invention of the sanitary system and modern medicine.

Although there have been industrial, pharmaceutical and computer technology advances, the humanity is still unable to control all the existing diseases and health deficiencies such as cancer, heart disease, diabetes, allergies, osteoporosis, obesity and other diseases, whose incidence is increasing (depression, Alzheimer's, myopia, autism, musculoskeletal disorders).

The purpose of the research: Global assessment of students from the rural areas of Moldova (from the South, Center and North of the country), to assess the impact of the deviation from normal anatomy, physiology or psychology and to record the existing deficit, from the simplest to the most complex ones in compared to existing standards. The obtained results will help us establish the direction of more active involvement in the process of children's development, recovery or treatment of diseases, their prevention in case of necessity.

Research methods: The evaluations carried out by us in this research will allow us to use a series of activities that will receive coefficients depending on the individual's ability to perform them, and in the end, a total result will be reached that orients us on the health status of the examined child. Thus, we used the anthropometric and somatoscopic evaluation method to assess height and body mass, as well as establish the Quetele index.

The motor tests have the aim to assess the abilities of children of secondary school age from the rural area, as well as the mathematical-statistical method of processing the acquired materials.

Results: Tables 1 - 4 present the results of ascertaining the physical and motor condition, as well as the presence of negative factors for the development of secondary class boys and girls from the Central, Northern and Southern localities of the country.

Thus, table 1 includes the statistical data obtained following the examination of children in terms of physical development (stature, body mass and the ratio between them according to the Quetele index, chest excursion), as well as the motor state, determined on the basis of tests that reflect the development of the main physical qualities and the presence of negative factors, such as: platypodia, scoliosis and obesity.

The table presents the comparative statistical analysis of the results obtained following the research of the indices related to the physical and motor condition of the boys in the secondary classes of the rural schools. The statistical analysis of physical development (especially height) shows that the boys in the secondary classes of rural schools from the localities of Center, North and South generally develop equally ($P > 0.05$).

The comparative analysis of body mass demonstrates that the boys from secondary classes in the South and North localities have relatively equal indices in terms of weight ($P > 0.05$). But the boys from the Center clearly exceed these indices ($P < 0.05$), in relation to their peers from the North and South. At the same time, according to the Quetele index, to the greatest extent the boys from the Center fall within the normal values (93.34%), followed by those from the South (68.34%) and, to a much lesser extent than the norm – the boys from the North (56.67%).

Table 1.

Evaluation of the physical and motor development of boys in the secondary school classes of educational institutions from the rural area of the Republic of Moldova

No. crt	Tests	Statistical characteristics $\bar{X} \pm m$			Comparative analysis					
		Center	North	South	1-2 Center-North		1-3 Center-South		2-3 North-South	
		1	2	3	t	P	t	P	t	P
I	Physical development									
1	Height (cm)	153,10 $\pm 2,99$	154,67 $\pm 2,06$	156,52 $\pm 2,99$	0,43	>0,05	0,81	>0,05	0,51	>0,05
2	Weight (kg)	57,23 $\pm 3,29$	46,81 $\pm 2,12$	50,79 $\pm 1,70$	2,66	<0,01	2,14	<0,05	1,47	>0,05
3	Chest Excursion (cm)	6,17 $\pm 0,52$	5,78 $\pm 0,37$	5,46 $\pm 0,82$	0,61	>0,05	0,79	>0,05	0,35	>0,05
4	Quetelet index (%)	93,34	56,67	68,34	—	—	—	—	—	—
II	Motor status									
1	Running-suveica 3x10m (sec)	8,74 $\pm 0,23$	8,13 $\pm 0,12$	8,28 $\pm 0,06$	2,62	<0,01	2,10	<0,05	1,15	>0,05
2	Standing long jump (cm)	164,87 $\pm 4,87$	170,20 $\pm 5,27$	169,18 $\pm 5,17$	0,74	>0,05	0,61	>0,05	0,14	>0,05
3	Push-ups from the support position with the hands on the gym bench (no. of repeats)	5,80 $\pm 1,49$	6,09 $\pm 1,07$	6,20 $\pm 1,04$	0,16	>0,05	0,22	>0,05	0,07	>0,05
4	Raising the trunk from the lying position (hands on the chest) in 30 sec. (no. of repeats)	23,52 $\pm 0,87$	24,13 $\pm 0,89$	25,55 $\pm 0,72$	0,49	>0,05	1,80	>0,05	1,24	>0,05
5	Forward bend on the gym bench (hands down) (cm)	8,32 $\pm 2,23$	9,50 $\pm 0,48$	8,44 $\pm 0,62$	0,52	>0,05	0,05	>0,05	1,36	>0,05

Note: P – 0,05; 0,01; 0,001;
t= 1,980; 2,618; 3,374.

In a certain sense, the physical development of boys in the secondary classes is reflected by the chest excursion indices, which characterize the development (state) of the respiratory system of their body. The study shows that the indices of the thoracic excursion of secondary class boys from rural schools are relatively equal in all localities included in the research ($P > 0,05$) [2].

In this way, the research on the level of physical development of secondary class boys from the Central, North and South rural localities demonstrates that, in most cases, their bodies and their physical status are formed in accordance with age-specific physiological indices. At the same time, the negative impact of social and environmental conditions can be seen on the level of physical development of these boys.

According to the majority of tests, whose indexes characterize strength and strength-speed capacities, as well as body flexibility, the regional development of secondary class boys is practically equal (irrelevant) in the conditions when $P > 0,05$. The exception is the results obtained in the 'running-suveica' test (which establishes the ability to develop speed and coordinate movement), which demonstrate that the boys from the North are clearly superior to their peers from the Center ($P > 0,01$). A relatively identical situation in the respective test is recorded for the boys from the South and the Center: the indices attested for boys from the South

proved to be clearly higher than those attested for boys from the Center ($P > 0,05$).

Therefore, in our opinion, the motor condition of secondary class boys from rural schools included in the study process is also determined by the reduced level of movement during classes. In the Center, the abilities to develop speed and to coordinate the movement of the boys in the given category are inferior to those attested for the boys from the North and the South.

Table 2 shows the results of studying the factors with a negative impact on the physical development of boys in the secondary classes of rural schools.

Thus, according to the number of platypody cases, students from the North are in first place (38.33%), the second place goes to the students from the Center (16.66%), and the third - to the students from the South (11.66%). According to the number of cases of scoliosis among middle school boys, the ranking is as follows: students from the North - 15.00%; students from the Center - 10.00%; students from the South - 5.83%.

The cases of early-stage obesity among boys in the researched category were recorded in greater numbers in the North district (43.33%), followed, in descending order, by those in the South (31.66%) and those in the Center with insignificant indices (6.66%). These quotas are correlated with their indexes, compared to the norms according to the Quetele index, respectively: 56.67%; 68.34%; 93.34%.

Table 2.

The existence of ailments at the boys in secondary rural schools from the Republic of Moldova

No crt.	Negative factors of physical development	Center	North	South	Average index	Distribution of places according to negative factors		
						I	II	III
1	Platypodia %	16,66	38,33	11,66	22,22	North	Center	South
2	Scoliosis %	10,00	15,00	5,83	10,28	North	Center	South
3	Obesity %	6,66	43,33	31,66	27,22	North	South	Center

Under these conditions, the results of the research carried out among secondary class boys from rural schools located in the Center, North and South indicate the fact that, according to physical development, all the children in question evolve in accordance with the physiological laws specific to their age and with the existing regional peculiarities, including those of negative order.

In most cases, the motor condition of the boys in the respective category (secondary classes, rural localities) is relatively identical in the entire area under research. The only exception is the ability to develop speed and coordinate movements, which differ from case to case, depending on the level of motor activity during the lessons.

Moreover, the poor movement condition of the boys included in the present study correlates with the presence of some negative manifestations, such as platypodia, scoliosis and obesity. These negative manifestations represent the factors that restrain motor activity and are attested in all the investigated rural localities, but especially in the North, where the highest average index is recorded – 32.22%.

The separate assessment of boys and girls was dictated by the need for accurate assessments comparable to existing standards. Tables 3 and 4 present the results of the physical and motor condition assessment, as well as the presence of negative development factors in secondary class girls from the Central, North and South localities.

Thus, in table 3 are included the statistical data obtained from the examination of the children in terms of physical development (stature, body mass and the ratio between them according to the Quetele index, chest excursion), as well as in terms of motor state. The study is based on tests that reflect the development of the main physical qualities and the presence of negative factors, such as platypodia, scoliosis and obesity.

The statistical analysis of physical development (namely: by stature indices, body mass, chest excursion (circumference of the chest)) shows that the girls in the secondary classes of rural schools from the localities of Center, North and South generally develop equally ($P > 0.05$), under the conditions of an insignificant reduction of the Quetele index. In the given context, the highest index of the height-body mass ratio among secondary class girls from rural schools was recorded by those from the Center (86.67%), followed by the girls from the South (76.67%) and those from the North with the lowest values (57.78%).

Thus, the research of physical development of girls from the given category shows that, in most cases, their bodies and physical status are formed in accordance with age-specific physiological indices. However, the negative impact of social and environmental conditions on girls is, to a certain extent, higher than in the case of boys in the same school category.

The study of the results regarding the motor condition of secondary class girls from the Central, North and South rural localities proves the following fact: in the most of the tests that characterize strength and strength-speed capacities, as well as body flexibility, the level of regional development is practically identical (irrelevant) in all localities ($P > 0.05$).

The only exception is the results of the 'running-suveica' test, which determines the capacities for speed development and coordination of movements. According to this test, girls from the North and South have a relatively identical level of developing these capacities ($P > 0.05$) and they are clearly superior to their peers from the Center ($P < 0.05$). According to other tests results, which targeted the movement capacities of the girls from secondary classes involved in the study, there are no relevant differences between the regions ($P > 0.05$).

In that context, we consider that the motor condition of the girls in the secondary classes of the rural schools has an insufficient level of motor activity during the class hours. In addition, it was established that in the Center, the coordination-speed and strength-speed capacities of girls from the targeted category are deficient compared to those attested for girls from the North and South.

The examination of the negative factors for physical development of the secondary class girls from rural schools demonstrates that the girls from the North are in first place (36.66%) according to the number of platypodia cases; in second place are those from the Center (21.66%) and the girls from the South with the index of 13.33%. According to the number of scoliosis cases, within the same sample, the places were distributed as follows: I – girls from the North (16.67%); II - girls from the Center and those from the South with the same index - 10.00%. The highest number of early stage obesity was also recorded among girls from the North (42.22%), which is extremely alarming. In the South, only 23.33% of the girls subjected to testing suffer from obesity in the early stages, and in the Center this index is only 13.33%. These results correlate with the normative values according to the Quetele index.

Table 3.

Evaluation of the physical and motor development of secondary school girls in the rural area of the Republic of Moldova

No Crt.	Test	Statistical characteristics			Comparative analysis					
		$\bar{X} \pm m$			1-2 Center-North		1-3 Center-South		2-3 North-South	
		Center	North	South	t	P	T	P	t	P
		1	2	3						
I	Physical development									
1	Height (cm)	153,42 ±3,01	153,54 ±1,84	152,60 ±2,23	0,03	>0,05	0,21	>0,05	0,32	>0,05
2	Weight (kg)	44,65 ±3,54	45,75 ±2,32	47,18 ±2,11	0,26	>0,05	0,61	>0,05	0,45	>0,05
3	Chest Excursion (cm)	5,91 ±0,71	5,17 ±0,42	6,15 ±0,39	0,90	>0,05	0,29	>0,05	1,72	>0,05
4	Quetelet index (%)	86,67	57,78	76,67	—	—	—	—	—	—
II	Motor status									
1	Running-suveica 3x10m (sec)	9,49 ±0,31	8,62 ±0,22	8,74 ±0,09	2,29	<0,05	2,34	<0,05	0,50	>0,05
2	Standing long jump (cm)	152,75 ±9,41	152,22 ±4,20	157,52 ±3,66	0,05	>0,05	0,47	>0,05	0,95	>0,05
3	Push-ups from the support position with the hands on the gym bench (no. of repeats)	5,77 ±1,76	5,71 ±1,15	5,54 ±1,09	0,03	>0,05	0,11	>0,05	0,11	>0,05
4	Raising the trunk from the lying position (hands on the chest) in 30 sec. (no. of repeats)	20,35 ±1,58	21,38 ±0,89	23,12 ±0,94	0,57	>0,05	1,50	>0,05	1,35	>0,05
5	Forward bend on the gym bench (hands down) (cm)	9,56 ±2,86	8,83 ±0,83	8,06 ±1,37	0,24	>0,05	0,47	>0,05	0,48	>0,05

Note: P – 0,05; 0,01; 0,001;
t= 1,980; 2,618; 3,374.

In this context, the research carried out among the secondary class girls from the rural schools in the Center, North and South demonstrate that they evolve in accordance with the age-specific physiological laws and the existing regional peculiarities, including the negative ones.

The motor condition of the girls in the researched category, in most cases, demonstrates practically absolute similarities in all localities and, in general, reflects a deficient motor activism during class hours.

In addition, this deficient state is also conditioned by factors with a negative impact, including platypodia, scoliosis and obesity, as restraining factors in motor manifestations.

Table 4.

The existence of negative factors of physical development at the girls in secondary rural schools from the Republic of Moldova

No crt.	Negative factors of physical development	Center	North	South	Average index	Distribution of places according to negative factors		
						I	II	III
1	Platypodia %	21,66	36,66	13,33	23,88	North	Center	South
2	Scoliosis %	10,00	16,67	10,00	12,22	North	Center South	—
3	Obesity %	13,33	42,22	23,33	26,29	North	South	Center

The greatest presence of these negative factors was recorded for the girls from the North and South, while in the Center they are insignificant.

Conclusions:

1. According to the level of physical development, the secondary school students from rural schools from the Center, North and South evolve in accordance

with age-specific physiological laws and existing regional peculiarities.

2. The motor condition of the boys and girls in the secondary classes of the rural schools included in the given research can be characterized by the following thesis: in the most cases, its level is identical in all

localities, reflecting, in general, a lack of movement activism during class hours. In addition, this lack of movement (for both girls and boys) correlates with the presence of negative factors, including platypodia, scoliosis and obesity. As factors holding back movement activism, they are attested in all student groups, subject to research, but the highest indices are recorded in the North and South.

3. Regrettably, in rural schools, in general, and in those included in this research, in particular, the activity of preventing or, at least, reducing the rates of development of platypodia, scoliosis and obesity it is not organized and ensured at the appropriate level.

References

1. Marcu V. Perspectives in approaching the practice of physical exercises by "exempt" students. Bucharest, 2001, 238 p.
2. Mîrza D. The theoretical-methodical bases of physical exercise. Course notes. Bacău: Plumb Publishing House, 2007. 303 p.
3. Todea S. F. Physical exercise in physical education, sports and physical therapy. Bucharest: Romania of tomorrow. Foundation Publishing House, 2009. 280 p.
4. Zavalîșca A., Tuchilă I., Demcenco P. The particularities of rehabilitation of students with physical deficiencies in the gymnasium cycle in the process of physical education: monograph. Chisinau, 2010.